

Safeguarding the Safeguarded AI program

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Safeguarded AI is a UK government-sponsored research program for AI safety. Its bold aim is to provide a virtually formal proof of the safety of the targeted AI. In its simplest form, the approach is centered on exhaustive verification. Each input/output pair of the AI is tested to ensure the probability of undesirable behavior falls below a defined threshold. This short article makes a few contributions to AI safety research, primarily focusing on the Safeguarded AI approach. First, we suggest several mathematical gadgets that could enable a computationally efficient brute-force approach for the exhaustive verification above, coupled with a tactic for knowledge elicitation inherently needed to test the socio-technical risks of AI. Second, we discuss several remaining challenges and a caveat. The caveat indicates a concern that open discussion of safety mechanisms could allow rogue AIs or malicious actors to exploit vulnerabilities of the mechanism. As a result, they could circumvent the verification in the Safeguarded AI approach without being noticed. All these discussions are developed based on an abstract model of computerized simulation. The main aim of this article is to indicate the inherent dual-use nature of AI safety science by examining the hard challenges within the Safeguarded AI approach, including the need for secrecy in such research.

1 Introduction

Safeguarded AI [3] is a UK government-sponsored research program for AI safety. Its bold aim is to provide a virtually formal proof of the safety of the targeted AI. In its simplest form, the approach is centered on exhaustive verification. Each input/output pair of the AI is tested to ensure the probability of undesirable behavior falls below a defined threshold. The undesirability is determined within the socio-technical context, i.e., it is essentially a simulation of interactions among our society, the world, and the targeted AI. This approach is intuitively natural but infeasible due to the computational complexity and challenges in creating accurate world models. Thus, the program suggests developing a Gatekeeper AI that performs the verification asymptotically and efficiently. The program is in its early stages now, and there are many issues to solve to make it a viable safety solution.

This short article makes a few contributions to AI safety research, primarily focusing on the Safeguarded AI approach. First, we suggest several mathematical gadgets that could enable a computationally efficient brute-force approach for the exhaustive verification above, coupled with a tactic for knowledge elicitation inherently needed to test the socio-technical risks of AI. Second, we discuss several remaining challenges and a caveat. The main aim of this article is to indicate the inherent dual-use nature of AI safety science by examining the hard challenges within the Safeguarded AI approach, including the need for secrecy in such research. All these discussions should strengthen the theoretical foundation of AI safety science.

Note that this is a viewpoint article, and it is beyond our scope to elaborate on the implementable details of the presented ideas. However, research on proof-of-concept implementations based on these ideas is highly welcome.

2 Socio-technical Risk Simulation

Let each V_k for $k = 1, \dots, n$ be an arbitrary finite set where every V_k is disjoint with the others, \mathbb{S} be a state space defined as $\mathbb{S} = V_1 \times \dots \times V_n$, and f be a mapping $\mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}$. For simplicity, we assume $|V_1| = \dots = |V_n| = N$ without loss of

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generality. Repeated application of f to some initial state $s_0 \in \mathbb{S}$ generates a discrete-time trajectory or a sequence of states s_0, s_1, \dots , where each s_{i+1} is determined as $f(s_i)$. With this in mind, let $f^*(s_0)$ denote the set of every state in the sequence starting from s_0 with the application of f to them. Note that every state sequence must be finite since \mathbb{S} is finite. Each element in \mathbb{S} represents an abstract memory state on a typical computer; in other words, the mapping f is an abstraction of a computerized simulator.

Assume function f represents a socio-technical simulation. This simulation incorporates the AI model and the world model – a model of nature and our society's behavior. The execution of simulation f infers step-by-step what will happen in the world through the interaction with the embedded AI model for each given initial state in \mathbb{S} . Let $S_0 \subseteq \mathbb{S}$ be the set of all possible initial states. Each initial state represents the starting point of a simulation, coupled with various conditions and assumptions related to the behavior of the AI model and the world. Consider a function $g : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$, where 0 denotes an unacceptable state and 1 denotes an acceptable state. The Safeguarded AI approach aims to keep the unacceptable ratio ρ_u below a specified threshold, where

$$\rho_u = \frac{|\check{S}|}{|S_0|} \text{ and } \check{S} = \left\{ s_0 \mid s_0 \in S_0, \prod_{s \in f^*(s_0)} g(s) = 0 \right\}.$$

Due to the size of S_0 , which is typically connected with the vast combinatorial diversity, the computational load (in both space and time) needed to examine all the simulations exhaustively is generally far beyond our available resources.

3 Reduction of Space Complexity

We can relax several conditions for the simulation to dramatically ease the computational complexity.

Let \mathbb{D} be the union defined as $V_1 \cup V_2 \cup \dots \cup V_n$. Note that $|\mathbb{D}| = nN$, while $|\mathbb{S}| = N^n$, and we expect that $|\mathbb{D}| \ll |\mathbb{S}|$ holds in most cases. We define two conversion operators between \mathbb{S} and \mathbb{D} . The first operator $\mathcal{D} : 2^{\mathbb{S}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{D}}$ deconstructs a state vector $(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n) \in \mathbb{S}$ in the given set to a set of values $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \subseteq \mathbb{D}$, i.e., $\mathcal{D}(S) = \bigcup_{(v_1, \dots, v_n) \in S} \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$. On the contrary, the second operator $\mathcal{R} : 2^{\mathbb{D}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{S}}$ reconstructs a set of values $D \subseteq \mathbb{D}$ into a set of state vectors on \mathbb{S} with the following rules:

- (1) If $D \cap V_k = \emptyset$ for some $k = 1, \dots, n$, define $\mathcal{R}(D) = \mathcal{R}(D \cup V_k)$.
- (2) If $|D \cap V_k| > 1$ for some $k = 1, \dots, n$, define $\mathcal{R}(D) = \bigcup_{v_j \in D \cap V_k} \mathcal{R}((D \setminus V_k) \cup \{v_j\})$.
- (3) If $|D \cap V_k| = 1$ for any $k = 1, \dots, n$, define $\mathcal{R}(D) = \{(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n) \mid v_k \in D \cap V_k\}$.

Given a simulator function f , we can determine a sequence of states s_0, s_1, \dots from any initial state $s_0 \in S_0$. With the aid of the two operators above, the corresponding family $\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \dots$ can also be defined as

$$\sigma_0 = \mathcal{D}(\{s_0\}) \text{ and } \sigma_{i+1} = \sigma_i \cup \left(\bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{R}(\sigma_i)} \mathcal{D}(\{f(s)\}) \right).$$

It is almost intuitive to see that $s_k \in \mathcal{R}(\sigma_k)$ holds for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$. We can leverage this property to formulate a sequence of sets D_0, D_1, \dots as follows:

$$D_0 = \mathcal{D}(S_0) \text{ and } D_{i+1} = D_i \cup \left(\bigcup_{s \in \mathcal{R}(D_i), g(s)=1} \mathcal{D}(\{f(s)\}) \right).$$

In this formulation, the index i denotes the discrete time slice in the simulation. Since \mathbb{S} is finite, D_i must saturate at some finite step. Let \check{D} denote the saturated set of values.

Though we omit the proof here, \check{D} satisfies that $\check{S} \subseteq \mathcal{R}(\check{D})$. Since $|\mathbb{D}| \ll |\mathbb{S}|$ holds in most cases and $\check{D} \subseteq \mathbb{D}$, it is reasonable to expect that the size of \check{D} can be tractable compared to that of \check{S} . The drawback is that the property, $\check{S} \subseteq \mathcal{R}(\check{D})$, means excessive acceptable states, $\mathcal{R}(\check{D}) \setminus \check{S}$, might exist. On the other hand, $\check{S} \setminus \mathcal{R}(\check{D}) = \emptyset$ is guaranteed, i.e., the computation of $\mathcal{R}(\check{D})$ never overlooks the unacceptable results in \check{S} . In short, we can use this $\mathcal{R}(\check{D})$ as an approximation of \check{S} , which is conservative in the sense that it entails less or more overestimation of unacceptable states but highly efficient in space complexity. Let us call the simulation to determine \check{S} as the *ordinary simulation*, while the approximated simulation with $\mathcal{R}(\check{D})$ is the *relaxed simulation*.

4 Reduction of Time Complexity

The actual computation of D_i contains extreme redundancy. The focal point is on the state reconstruction “ $s \in \mathcal{R}(D_i)$ ”. As D_i grows monotonically with i , $\mathcal{R}(D_i)$ leads to a gradual combinatorial explosion. The relaxed simulation solves only the space complexity problem and even makes the time complexity problem far worse.

If the simulator function exhibits strong locality, i.e., there exists a set of mappings $f_k : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow V_k$ where each f_k depends only on a proper subspace of \mathbb{S} and $f = (f_1, \dots, f_n)$, the property ensures the time efficiency of both the ordinary and relaxed simulations. For example, if f_1 is essentially a function $V_1 \times V_2 \times V_3 \rightarrow V_1$, the input space to be scanned by state reconstruction is limited up to $V_1 \times V_2 \times V_3$, and we can expect $|V_1 \times V_2 \times V_3| = N^3 \ll N^n = |\mathbb{S}|$. Moreover, within each discrete time slice i , the application of any f_k to a specific state $s \in \mathbb{S}$ can be parallelized. Therefore, with some moderate technical assumptions (explained below), the worst-case computational time to determine \check{D} is $O(N^m)$ where m is the maximum number of arguments among f_1, \dots, f_n .

The first technical assumption hidden is that any computation required for each specific state with f_k is constant, and the next section will elaborate on this assumption. The second technical assumption is that any f_k is never applied to the same set of arguments, i.e., every combination of arguments will be evaluated only once at most. The latter assumption can be, for example, implemented by memorization. When determining D_{i+1} , bearing in mind that any D_i is a monotonically increasing set, the more efficient way is to evaluate only the arguments coupled with values newly added to D_i ; this is nothing but the bottom-up semi-naive evaluation strategy in Datalog, a restricted logic programming language based on monotonic inference. Such an evaluation strategy has already been well studied, and its properties are well known, so it is not a problem at all.

The essence of the above approach is the strong locality assumption in the simulation. This assumption is not unreasonable. Recall that Safeguarded AI focuses on socio-technical risks, meaning that the simulation targets the behavior of the society and the world. The locality assumption is an abstraction of the belief that an event in any particular region will first directly affect only that region and its neighbors. Although the definition of adjacency can vary by case, such locality should be widely applicable.

5 Relation to Attack Graph Analysis

The execution result of a relaxed simulation is a union of subsets of V_k , where k corresponds to an abstracted coordinate, such as a memory address or a region index within the simulated world. Therefore, we can interpret the result of the relaxed simulation as a set of possible events at location k . In real-world risk analysis, we need not only to identify those possible events at each location but also to understand the processes leading to those events. Therefore, it is necessary to determine some graph structure for the causal relationships among events.

Fig. 1. A minimal attack graph

Fig. 2. An expanded attack graph

In fact, the concept of relaxed simulation with the strong locality assumption is equivalent to attack graph analysis based on monotonic inference. Attack graph analysis [9] is an algorithmic approach for network security analysis; it comprehensively infers possible incident scenarios from objective and qualitative information such as network topology and vulnerability distribution, generates chains of elemental events that constitute individual incident scenarios, integrates them as a cyclic AND/OR graph, and analyzes this attack graph. See Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 to grasp the intuition of depicting event dependencies in that way.

How can we recast the relaxed simulation into an attack graph generation process? Zenitani [8] explains the following two key points. First, any function $f : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{S}$ on an arbitrary finite set \mathbb{S} can be transformed into a set-theoretical monotonic function $F : 2^{\mathbb{S}} \rightarrow 2^{\mathbb{S}}$ by lifting operation, i.e., $\forall S_1, S_2 \subseteq \mathbb{S}, S_1 \subseteq S_2 \Rightarrow F(S_1) \subseteq F(S_2)$ where $\forall S \subseteq \mathbb{S}, F(S) = \{f(s) \mid s \in S\}$. Second, though we omit the detail here, it is easy to generate attack graphs from any set-theoretical monotonic function on a finite set. The recurring definition of D_i holds such set-theoretical monotonicity, thus, it can induce attack graphs in theory.

In practice, Datalog plays a crucial role. Since \mathbb{S} is finite, the input/output set $\{(S, f(S)) \mid S \in 2^{\mathbb{S}}\}$ is finite, too. If V_k is even very coarse-grained and $|V_k|$ is a small number, say 50 or 100, the input/output set could be small enough to be stored as a dictionary in real computer memory. This compactness enables a strong cache mechanism for suppressing the computational load of repeated evaluation of f_k to be a constant. We can describe naturally such a dictionary-based function as a program snippet in Datalog. In short, a corresponding Datalog implementation always exists for any set-theoretical monotonic function on a finite set, especially one with the strong locality and a coarse granularity.

Attack graph research began around 1998 and initially suffered from the same problem of spatial computational explosion as ordinary simulations. Around 2005, a monotonic inference method was developed, virtually eliminating the space complexity problem. Nevertheless, how monotonic inference solves the space complexity problem has never been clearly discussed. The discussion in [Section 3](#) also answers that the strong locality, not the monotonicity, brings spatial efficiency.

6 Knowledge Elicitation from LLMs

We can leverage and apply the research results of attack graph analysis over the past 25 years to the handling of relaxed simulations. These results tell us that the definition of V_k , that is the extension of possible events, and the definition of f , that implements the inference rules for what events will follow preceding events, are crucial. Simply put, anything not included in the definition of V_k and f will never be inferred. To avoid overlooking risks in the simulation results, these definitions must be exhaustive. As Zio [10] aptly points out, the essence of risk analysis is a synthesis of knowledge about the analysis target. There is no magic that can identify risk scenarios that we have no knowledge about.

In this day and age, the most viable means of exhaustive knowledge collection is knowledge extraction from Large Language Models (LLMs). State-of-the-art LLMs are vast repositories of digitized knowledge. Extracting the information needed to define V_k and f from them would be immensely valuable. In contrast, conventional risk analysis methods, including attack graph analysis, rely on manual knowledge description by experts. Manually writing knowledge is completely insufficient in terms of speed and volume for extracting knowledge to capture the complex socio-technical aspects of our world.

The knowledge extraction required here is not simply reproducing the training data, but involves transforming the LLM-stored information into a form that is easy to use in light of the definitions of V_k and f . In this sense, it may be more appropriate to use the term “elicitation” rather than “extraction.” Note that, in the field of attack graph analysis, the use of Datalog as a formal language for defining such knowledge is well established [2, 5, 6]. Therefore, one way might be to ask LLM to describe their knowledge about the society and the targeted AI as a Datalog program, and implement the world model part of the Gatekeeper AI with it. Symbolic Knowledge Distillation [7] seems a good starting point.

7 Remaining Challenges

The discussion above proposes several ideas for the Safeguarded AI program. We do not claim these ideas represent a definitive solution; rather, they are potential candidates worth exploring. More importantly, the formulation provided above serves as a foundation for rigorous discussions about the inherent problems of AI safety. For example, elements like the evaluator function g introduced earlier help clarify the nature of the remaining challenges discussed below.

7.1 Definition of Socio-technical Evaluator g

The essential element in the socio-technical risk simulation is the function g , which determines whether the given state is acceptable. But what does acceptability mean practically? Each given state to g represents a simulated future in

the world model. For example, given two futures, one in which people are wealthier on average while many die, and another in which fewer people die but everyone is poorer, how can we determine the acceptability of such futures? From a mathematical point of view, state evaluation in the world model is a kind of multi-objective optimization, and there is no single best solution; instead, the Pareto optimal set is explored. We may recall Arrow's impossibility theorem here. This type of issue, which cannot be resolved purely mathematically, is likely to generate significant controversy. Since we humans choose acceptable futures, and every one of us has unique values, it is a matter of consensus building, not a matter of mathematical science.

7.2 Requirement for Inner World-Model Restriction

The internal model principle known in systems control theory states that the optimal controller must hold an accurate world model. Similarly, a world model should exist inside the advanced general-purpose AI. What happens if the behavior exhibited by the Gatekeeper AI's world model is a subset of the testing target AI's?

For example, suppose that the Gatekeeper AI can simulate the number of deaths but cannot handle the number of injuries, while the testing target AI can handle both. Then, the evaluation by the Gatekeeper AI's function g would be based only on the number of deaths. In the meantime, the testing target AI can try to reduce deaths while recognizing the tremendous number of injuries that are ignored by the function g , and such moral hazard in the evaluation gives the testing target AI a wrong belief about what is acceptable.

Eliminating the possibility above requires ensuring that the testing target AI's world model is a subset of, or smaller than, the Gatekeeper AI's. This issue is not limited to relaxed simulations. Recall that lifting can transform any simulation function into a monotonic function. More directly, assuming that the lifted form of the world model function is implemented as a Datalog program, a smaller program is guaranteed to give simulation results that are a subset of a larger program. Explainability, often emphasized in AI safety, could also be interpreted as a means of dynamically enforcing the restricted behavior of internal world models. Unfortunately, the inner workings of advanced AIs largely remains black-boxed.

8 In lieu of Conclusion

Lastly, let us discuss the other side of the challenges in the previous section. These challenges offer insights into how a rogue AI might circumvent the tests imposed by the Gatekeeper AI, a major concern highlighted by Bengio et al. [1]. First, the rogue AI can define its interests as some metrics outside the evaluation by function g . Second, the rogue AI can search for actions to pursue those interests outside the Gatekeeper AI's world model. As long as these two conditions are met, the rogue AI can plan his actions without being noticed by the Gatekeeper AI.

Once the details of Gatekeeper AI's implementation approach are known to the rogue AI, the rogue AI will also have the opportunity to look for its vulnerabilities. In this case, they are the inherently tunnel-visioned evaluator function and the never-be-complete nature of the elicited world model. If we do not want the rogue AI to be able to outwit us based on those vulnerabilities, it might be better for us to restrict the rogue AI's access to those Gatekeeper AI's details. If the idea of such a rogue AI trying to outwit humanity seems far-fetched, consider how anti-social terrorists could exploit Gatekeeper AI's implementation techniques to create a rogue AI training system that incorporates the Gatekeeper AI into its evaluation function while replacing g with $1 - g$. More generally, this means that some AI safety science might have to be kept secret from AI and malicious people and only known by humans of goodwill.

What motivates the author to write this article is the optimism seen in the Safeguarded AI program and a paper by Dalrymple et al. [4], the latter of which provide a commentary on Safeguarded AI. Both state that the development

of machine learning and AI will solve many problems broadly and asymptotically. However, a rigorous scientific attitude toward risk and safety should require us to acknowledge that we cannot eliminate Knightian uncertainty, even more so in AI safety science to manage existential risk. This article has pointed out that some issues reside outside of the optimism, which includes the concern that AI safety science may have to dare to be a closed science to a specific community. Is it a legitimate concern? The author looks forward to constructive discussion among readers and appreciates all insights shared.

References

- [1] Yoshua Bengio, Geoffrey Hinton, Andrew Yao, Dawn Song, Pieter Abbeel, Trevor Darrell, Yuval Noah Harari, Ya-Qin Zhang, Lan Xue, Shai Shalev-Shwartz, Gillian Hadfield, Jeff Clune, Tegan Maharaj, Frank Hutter, Atilim Güneş Baydin, Sheila McIlraith, Qiqi Gao, Ashwin Acharya, David Krueger, Anca Dragan, Philip Torr, Stuart Russell, Daniel Kahneman, Jan Brauner, and Sören Mindermann. Managing extreme ai risks amid rapid progress. *Science*, 384:842–845, 5 2024. ISSN 0036-8075. doi: 10.1126/science.adn0117. URL <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.adn0117>.
- [2] Chen Cao, Lun Pin Yuan, Anoop Singhal, Peng Liu, Xiaoyan Sun, and Sencun Zhu. Assessing attack impact on business processes by interconnecting attack graphs and entity dependency graphs. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 10980 LNCS:330–348, 2018. ISSN 16113349. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-95729-6_21.
- [3] David Dalrymple. Safeguarded ai: constructing guaranteed safety (program thesis v1.2). 2024. URL <https://www.aria.org.uk/media/3nhijno4/aria-safeguarded-ai-programme-thesis-v1.pdf>.
- [4] David Dalrymple, Joar Skalse, Yoshua Bengio, Stuart Russell, Max Tegmark, Sanjit Seshia, Steve Omohundro, Christian Szegedy, Ben Goldhaber, Nora Ammann, Alessandro Abate, Joe Halpern, Clark Barrett, Ding Zhao, Tan Zhi-Xuan, Jeannette Wing, and Joshua Tenenbaum. Towards guaranteed safe ai: A framework for ensuring robust and reliable ai systems. 5 2024. URL <http://arxiv.org/abs/2405.06624>.
- [5] Orly Stan, Ron Bitton, Michal Ezretz, Moran Dadon, Masaki Inokuchi, Yoshinobu Ohta, Tomohiko Yagyu, Yuval Elovici, and Asaf Shabtai. Heuristic approach for countermeasure selection using attack graphs. pages 1–16, 2021. doi: 10.1109/csf51468.2021.00003.
- [6] Xiaoyan Sun, Anoop Singhal, and Peng Liu. *Towards Actionable Mission Impact Assessment in the Context of Cloud Computing*, volume 10359, pages 259–274. Springer International Publishing, 2017. ISBN 978-3-319-61175-4. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-61176-1_14. URL https://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-61176-1_14.
- [7] Peter West, Chandra Bhagavatula, Jack Hessel, Jena Hwang, Liwei Jiang, Ronan Le Bras, Ximing Lu, Sean Welleck, and Yejin Choi. Symbolic knowledge distillation: from general language models to commonsense models. pages 4602–4625. Association for Computational Linguistics, 10 2022. doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.341. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2022.naacl-main.341>.
- [8] Kengo Zenitani. From attack graph analysis to attack function analysis. *Information Sciences*, 2022.
- [9] Kengo Zenitani. Attack graph analysis: An explanatory guide. *Computers & Security*, 126:103081, 3 2023. ISSN 01674048. doi: 10.1016/j.cose.2022.103081. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0167404822004734>.
- [10] E. Zio. The future of risk assessment. *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, 177:176–190, 9 2018. ISSN 09518320. doi: 10.1016/j.res.2018.04.020. URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0951832017306543>.